

Climate Based Crop Planning with Disease Prevention Through Data Intelligent Decision Making

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Abstract— In today's rapidly evolving agricultural landscape, characterized by technological advancements and dynamic climate conditions, farmers are faced with the challenge of optimizing crop planning while mitigating disease risks. This paper presents a novel approach to crop planning, focusing on climate and soil conditions as key determinants. By harnessing advanced technologies like machine learning and data analysis, farmers can make sound decisions regarding crop selection, planting plans, and resource management. By integrating current weather forecasts and soil data, farmers can adapt their strategies to maximize profits and prevent disease outbreaks. Our user-friendly dashboard offers clear recommendations and predictions, empowering farmers to navigate climate variability with confidence. This research not only benefits farmers but also promotes sustainable farming practices, contributing to the resilience of rural communities worldwide. Through collaboration and innovation, we aim to equip farmers with the tools needed to thrive in today's complex agricultural environment while safeguarding against disease risks.

Keywords— Crop planning, Disease prevention, Resilient agriculture, Crop Prediction, Disease Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary agricultural milieu, characterized by rapid climate fluctuations and evolving disease risks, farmers confront the imperative to optimize crop planning strategies while safeguarding against potential threats. This paper elucidates a cutting-edge approach to crop planning, predicated on leveraging climate data for intelligent decision-making aimed at disease prevention. By intertwining advanced data analytics with insights gleaned from climatic patterns, farmers can embark on a trajectory of proactive crop management. This paradigm shift underscores

the pivotal role of data intelligence in fortifying agricultural resilience against disease outbreaks. Through the fusion of real-time climate forecasts, historical disease incidence data, and sophisticated analytical tools, farmers can delineate bespoke strategies for crop selection, planting schedules, and resource allocation.

The ultimate objective is to empower farmers with actionable insights derived from data-driven decision-making, thereby enabling them to navigate the intricacies of climate variability with confidence and efficacy. Furthermore, by advocating for the adoption of climate-based crop planning methodologies, this research endeavours to foster sustainable agricultural practices while bolstering the resilience of farming communities worldwide against the spectre of crop diseases.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature survey conducted for this paper encompasses a wide range of studies exploring various aspects of agricultural technology, data analysis, and decision-making processes. Several studies have focused on leveraging machine learning algorithms and deep learning methods to enhance crop prediction, disease detection, and recommendation systems in agriculture. For instance, researchers [1] proposed a website that employs machine learning and CNN algorithm modules to recommend the most suitable crop to grow based on soil qualities and provide advice on supplements usage. Similarly, another study [2] suggested a paradigm for utilizing deep learning and machine learning techniques for crop disease classification, crop and fertilizer recommendation. By employing convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for disease identification and regression algorithms for crop and fertilizer recommendation, the study aimed to improve agricultural productivity and sustainability.

Furthermore, a recommendation system for plant disease monitoring was presented in a study by researchers [3]. This system utilized machine learning techniques to provide real time feedback on crop diagnosis to small-scale farmers, with the goal of reducing food security issues in sub-Saharan Africa. Additionally, a study focused on data mining techniques in agriculture [4] explored the use of classification algorithms such as the C4.5 decision tree for soil fertility analysis and the Simple Moving Average (SMA) algorithm for rainfall prediction. The study aimed to extract hidden patterns from agricultural data to recommend suitable crops based on soil nutrients and rainfall patterns, contributing to

Manuscript Received May 5, 2024; Revised 15 May, 2024 and Published on May 30, 2024

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informed decision-making in agriculture.

Moreover, researchers [5] investigated the importance of accurate crop prediction and disease detection in agriculture, proposing a web-based system that predicts crop yield and identifies crop diseases using machine learning algorithms. Another study [6] emphasized the significance of agriculture in the economy and proposed a recommendation system based on soil data analysis and rainfall prediction using machine learning algorithms such as C4.5 and Multi Linear regression.

Additionally, a study by researchers [7] highlighted the role of agriculture in rural areas and proposed a smartphone-based diagnostic tool for crop diseases with real-time feedback. This tool aimed to empower farmers with the ability to diagnose crop diseases without expert assistance, ultimately improving crop production and food availability. Furthermore, a study [8] focused on the use of technology and analytics in agriculture to address issues such as incorrect crop selection and low crop yields. The study proposed a model that utilizes economic and environmental factors for crop selection and yield prediction, aiming to improve farmers' income and livelihoods.

Another study [9] explored the use of machine learning and deep learning techniques for crop recommendation and disease identification. The study highlighted the effectiveness of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in accurately identifying plant diseases and recommending high-yield crops. Moreover, a study [10] proposed a web-based system that recommends crops and fertilizers based on soil characteristics and provides advice on crop disease management. The system aimed to assist farmers in making informed choices about crop selection and tackling various diseases.

Furthermore, researchers [11] investigated plant disease monitoring with information feedback to small farmers, proposing a recommendation system based on query-response pairs and machine learning algorithms. The system aimed to provide farmers with timely advice on crop diseases and management practices, ultimately improving crop yields and food security. Lastly, a study [12] explored the role of data mining techniques in agriculture, focusing on soil fertility analysis and rainfall prediction using algorithms such as C4.5 and Simple Moving Average (SMA). The study aimed to extract hidden patterns from agricultural data to recommend suitable crops based on soil nutrients and rainfall patterns, contributing to informed decision-making in agriculture.

Overall, these studies collectively highlight the importance of technology and data-driven approaches in improving agricultural productivity, crop management, and food security. By leveraging machine learning, deep learning, and data mining techniques, researchers aim to equip farmers with the knowledge and utilities required to make sound decisions and increase crop yields in agricultural systems.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

1 Farmers today face formidable challenges in adapting to the swiftly evolving conditions of the agricultural market, all while striving to maintain the profitability and sustainability of their operations. Conventional planning methods, entrenched in outdated practices and lacking access to real-time market insights and weather forecasts, frequently result in suboptimal decisions. Compounding these issues is the limited availability of advanced tools, leaving farmers without the requisite guidance to make informed choices. This disparity highlights an urgent necessity for a solution that harnesses technology to provide farmers with actionable recommendations and predictive analytics, with a particular emphasis on soil-driven crop planning. By bridging the divide between farmers and market dynamics through innovative data-driven approaches, such a solution has the potential to revolutionize crop planning practices, enhance resilience, and cultivate enduring success in agriculture. Additionally, integrating disease prediction into this framework further fortifies farmers against unforeseen challenges, aligning with the overarching goal of ensuring sustainable agricultural practices and safeguarding farming communities against the adverse impacts of crop diseases.

IV. PROPOSED APPROACH

This research proposes a self-improving approach to machine learning, functioning in a closed loop. Information is gathered, utilized for refining a model, and subsequently, the model's insights guide ongoing data collection. This iterative process fosters continual learning and enhancement, resulting in increasingly precise predictions and superior outcomes with each iteration.

Figure 1: Flow of the proposed approach for Crop Prediction

The proposed system involves several key steps and components:

- i. Data Acquisition: The process begins with gathering raw data from relevant sources.
- ii. Data Preprocessing: The collected data undergoes cleaning, formatting, and transformation to ensure its suitability for model training.
- iii. Model Training: The pre-processed data is then fed into a chosen machine learning model, allowing it to train on

underlying patterns and relationships within the data.

iv. Prediction and Classification: Once trained, the model can be used to query for predictions or classifications on new, unseen data.

v. Data-Driven Insights: The predictions and classifications inform future data collection efforts. This can involve focusing on areas where the model struggles or tailoring data gathering based on the model's insights.

Disease Prediction and Prevention:

Figure 2: Flow of the proposed approach for Disease prediction

The proposed system involves several key steps and components:

- i. Image Acquisition: The process begins with taking input from the user as an image of leaf of infected crop.
- ii. Data Preprocessing: The collected data undergoes cleaning, formatting, and transformation to ensure its suitability for querying on the model.
- iii. Embedding Extraction: The processed image is transformed into Matrix formation. And the patterns are recognized and stored in a variable
- iv. Prediction and Classification: These patterns are queried into the already trained Classification model. The model is trained with already available dataset of various crop diseases segregated with respect to the leaf of the affected crop.

V. RELATED WORK

In the context of soil-driven crop planning, leveraging data-driven approaches and machine learning techniques has become increasingly prevalent. Essential libraries like NumPy, Pandas, and Scikit-learn are commonly employed for data preprocessing and model training. This workflow involves tasks such as handling missing values, scaling features, and creating training and testing sets to optimize crop selection and yield prediction.

Predictive Analytics:

Predictive analytics plays a crucial role in market-driven crop planning by utilizing historical market data, weather patterns, and agricultural inputs to forecast crop yields and

market demand. Techniques such as regression analysis and time series forecasting are employed to provide insights into future market trends and optimize crop selection strategies accordingly.

Decision Support Systems: Decision support systems (DSS) merge data analytics and modeling methods to aid farmers in making well-informed decisions concerning crop choices, planting timetables, and resource distribution. These systems employ machine learning algorithms to examine market patterns, recognize lucrative prospects, and manage risks, thereby boosting the effectiveness and profitability of agricultural activities.

Precision Agriculture: Precision agriculture techniques, enabled by advances in sensor technology and data analytics, allow for the precise management of inputs such as water resources, fertilizers, and other utilities based on real-time market information and field conditions. By maximizing resource utilization and minimizing waste, precision agriculture contributes to the sustainability and profitability of crop production in market-driven environments.

Logistic Regression: As a supervised learning approach, Logistic Regression is a frequently used algorithm for predicting categorical dependent variables based on independent variables. It predicts the probability of a categorical outcome, providing values between 0 and 1.

```

import pandas as pd

df = pd.read_csv('Crop_recommendation.csv')
df.head(6)

```

	N	P	K	temperature	humidity	ph	rainfall	label
0	90	42	43	20.879744	82.002744	6.502985	202.935536	rice
1	85	58	41	21.770462	80.319644	7.038096	226.655537	rice
2	60	55	44	23.004459	82.320763	7.840207	263.964248	rice
3	74	35	40	26.491096	80.158363	6.980401	242.864034	rice
4	78	42	42	20.130175	81.604873	7.628473	262.717340	rice
5	69	37	42	23.058049	83.370118	7.073454	251.055000	rice

Figure 3: Data set of Plants

```

with open('classifier.pkl', 'rb') as file:
    model = pickle.load(file)

prediction = model.predict([[90, 42, 41, 20.879744, 82.002744, 6.502985, 202.935536]])

prediction

```

```

array(['rice'], dtype=object)

```

Figure 4: Predication of crop according to the data set

Disease Prediction

For the Disease prediction and prevention module, we have implemented a predefined code available on GitHub at https://github.com/siddhardhan23/plant-disease-prediction-cnn-deep-learning-project/blob/main/model_training_notebook/Plant_Disease_Prediction_CNN_Image_Classifier.ipynb. This model was selected due to its high accuracy and vast Dataset.

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Our study focused on using advanced technology like machine learning to predict crop diseases based on climate conditions, aiming to help farmers make better decisions. By employing Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) technology, we achieved accurate detection of potential crop diseases. We also developed a user-friendly platform that provides real-time disease risk assessments and offers practical advice for prevention. Our approach ensures farmer privacy through federated learning, which gathers insights from different farming regions while protecting sensitive data. By categorizing diseases and providing tailored recommendations, we aim to improve agricultural efficiency and help farmers navigate climate challenges effectively. Through ongoing innovation, we strive to support sustainable farming practices and resilience in farming communities worldwide.

Figure 5: Crop Prediction

Plant Disease Classifier

Figure 6: Disease Prediction

Figure 7: Accuracy Graph for Crop Prediction

Figure 8: Accuracy Graph for Disease Prediction

Figure 9: Loas Graph for Crop Prediction

Figure 10: Loss Graph for Disease Prediction

CONCLUSION

The integration of climate-based crop planning with data-intelligent decision-making holds significant promise for enhancing agricultural resilience and sustainability. By leveraging advanced technologies and real-time data analytics, farmers can optimize crop planning strategies to mitigate disease risks while maximizing yields. This holistic approach not only improves farm profitability but also promotes long-term environmental stewardship. Continued research and investment in data-driven solutions are essential to further refine these methodologies and ensure their widespread adoption, ultimately fostering a more resilient and prosperous future for agriculture.

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